

PROBLEMS MET BY THE STUDENT LEADERS AND THEIR EFFECTS TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Abstract:

Student leadership is an important first step toward developing leadership abilities for both individuals and school student organizations. According to research, young student leaders acquired various character attributes as they fulfilled their tasks. However, there was less awareness of the leadership problems they encountered while performing their duties as student leaders. This descriptive-correlational study aimed to determine the correlation between the problems met by student leaders and their academic performance in the First Semester of the Academic Year 2023-2024 at Mandaue City College. The questionnaire was made through Google Forms and given out to target respondents online. This study used purposive sampling to choose the respondents, focusing only on school-based student leaders. It consisted of forty-seven (47) student leaders from four organizations within the education department at Mandaue City College, namely UNIED, NAMFIL, FEMATH, and SOFEE. To determine the correlation, the researchers used the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between the problems faced by student leaders and their academic performance. Based on the findings, the study recommended that student leaders should: (1) attend time management workshops to improve productivity and academic performance; (2) participate in conflict resolution training to effectively manage team conflicts; (3) engage in self-efficacy enhancement training to build confident leadership skills; and (4) consider future research using qualitative methods for deeper insights into leadership challenges. This method strives to understand better and address the problems that student leaders face, as well as to increase their overall effectiveness and academic performance.

Keywords: : student leaders, academic performance, time management, role conflict, self- efficacy

Introduction:

Student leaders play important roles in influencing campus culture, encouraging community involvement, and speaking for their peers' different points of view in the continually evolving world of education. Student leaders face many difficulties that go beyond the limits of their academic responsibilities as they manage the obligations of leadership. As student leaders, they take charge of their roles. Student leadership requires quite a lot of time and effort,

as well as duty and responsibility. It requires heart and passion when it comes to being a student leader; it was difficult to manage academics and personal time, but it also brings happiness to some in their position as student leaders.

A lot of research showed that student leaders contributed more to campus life, but it also pointed out that being a leader and keeping up with studies could cause conflicts. Student organizations served as valuable platforms for nurturing diverse leadership qualities. In these groups, students faced real-life leadership challenges and situations with lower risks, which contributed to their psychological growth and the development of diverse leadership skills according to Amirianzadeh et al. (2011) as cited in Mitra (2022). However, few studies have been conducted to assess the effect of student leadership experience on academic success. Among the few, some research contended that leadership experience may have negative effects on academic performance. On the one hand, student leaders studied harder than others in their academics and so gained higher grades according to Liu et al. (2015). Leadership, on the other hand, took time away from studies and may have caused such individuals to lose concentration on their work. As a result, leadership activities may have harmed academic performance according to Anderson et al. (2017) as cited in Deng et al. (2020).

The gap in this research was the lack of awareness regarding the specific difficulties encountered by student leaders and how these difficulties affected their academic performance. This study aimed to assess the relationship between the problems encountered by student leaders and their academic performance. Specifically, it sought to examine the academic performance of student leaders and the problems they encountered, such as time management, role conflict, and self-efficacy. It also aimed to identify the significant relationship between these variables. Furthermore, the study intended to develop possible enhancement leadership programs that could support and improve the academic performance of student leaders.

The goal of this research was to fill this gap and provide useful insights for student leaders, students, parents, teachers, researchers, and schools. The findings could lead to the development of programs and support systems that recognized and addressed the needs of student leaders. This could also help schools and teachers better support student leaders. Understanding their problems could lead to programs and support systems that would help them succeed in both their leadership roles as well as their academic success. By studying the problems met by student leaders, researchers hoped to find ways to make school easier for them. With the right support, student leaders could do well in both their leadership roles and their classes, making school a better experience for everyone.

Literature Review:

Student Leadership

Being a leader means having the ability to influence others to achieve a goal or a vision. Making instructional changes and even raising student academic achievement may both benefit greatly from strong leadership. In any event, there are many different leadership models and a great deal of school pioneering, so this simple assertion hides a complicated reality. Student leadership is crucial for students to develop essential leadership skills, as highlighted by Johnson (2018). Through student leadership roles, individuals enhanced their self-confidence and communication abilities, preparing them to lead others effectively in the future. Participation in environmental activities, as mentioned by Naye et al. (2024), equips student leaders with the necessary skills to influence their peers positively and contribute to sustainability efforts. Moreover, Black et al. (2014) emphasized the positive impact of leadership roles in schools on students, including improved time management, interpersonal skills, decision-making, conflict resolution, and public speaking abilities. However, becoming a proficient student leader requires dedicated effort and training, as stated by Hine (2013). Students must actively work on mastering various leadership skills such as communication, decision-making, organization, action planning, strategic thinking, and risk management. Furthermore, involvement in student leadership fosters teamwork, which is essential for success both in academic settings and in future workplaces. Research suggests that individuals with prior leadership experience, particularly in student roles, are more likely to assume leadership positions in their careers. Despite its benefits, student leadership comes with challenges, including time constraints and potential impacts on academic performance and communication. Balancing family responsibilities, particularly for student leaders who are also parents, adds another layer of difficulty. Nevertheless, the experience of student leadership offers numerous rewards, including socialization, increased self-esteem, and opportunities for personal growth and development. Overall, student leadership plays a significant role in shaping individuals' futures by providing valuable skills and experiences.

Time Management

Student leaders' physical, emotional, and mental well-being have a direct impact on how effectively they manage their time. Typically, student leaders are among the busiest pupils in the school. As a student leader, you have to balance your involvement in student council, extracurriculars, family time, and academics. Student leaders who have the time to accomplish what they want to do are hard to come by. Effective time management can be highly difficult for students handling leadership responsibilities and academics. It involves serious preparation and limits ample time. According to Sahito et al. (2016), time management is a technique for allocating time under the demands of various tasks and activities to assure organizational performance and maximize benefits by using, saving, and not wasting time or energy. Effective time management techniques can assist people in reaching their objectives by determining and organizing the tasks required to finish their plans, boosting output, and elevating their level of job satisfaction according to Zafarullah and Pertti (2017).

Role Conflict

The conflicting obligations faced by students can create significant stress as they strive to fulfill all of them simultaneously. This phenomenon, known as "role conflict," is a primary reason for student drop-outs. Role conflict occurs when the pressures from one role clash with those from another. In the context of balancing work and college, role conflict often arises after attempting to achieve role balance. This conflict manifests as stress or anxiety stemming from incompatible responsibilities within a single role or across multiple roles. While extensively studied in the work/family domain, limited research addresses the interaction between students' roles and employment, leading to role conflict. This conflict, termed work-school conflict (WSC), can result in stress, absenteeism, and turnover. Buda and Lenaghan's (2005) study thoroughly explored this connection. WSC encompasses three main types of conflict: time-based, strain-based, and behavior-based. Time-based conflicts occur when time devoted to one role interferes with another, strain-based conflicts arise when strain from one role spills over into another, and behavior-based conflicts emerge when behaviors essential for one role contradict those necessary for another. Several researchers, including Oliveira (2008) and Van (2016), have identified time management as one of the most challenging aspects of balancing multiple responsibilities.

Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in their capacity to perform a given task, stemming from a cognitive appraisal of personal and environmental factors according to Schunk & Pajares (2004). High self-efficacy increased student engagement and success and, in return, engagement and success increased self-efficacy as stated by Schunk & Mullen (2012). Viewing self-efficacy as occurring within the educational interface acknowledges the complex array of intersecting institutional and student-based factors, which influence a student's belief in their capabilities. It also highlighted that self-efficacy may be one of the key mechanisms that could cause non-traditional students to be less engaged. All factors underpin the challenges facing non-traditional student groups and they concur with these authors that more research was needed on academic self-efficacy in non-traditional students, which is why self-efficacy was also a challenge for student leaders, as described by RJ (2023).

Among these responsibilities include helping students with their academic. Additionally, administrative issues, the development of peer and professional counseling, and general welfare services such as requesting funding support for financially disadvantaged students according to Luescher (2009). Representing and assisting students is the goal of student leadership. Consequently, as part of their responsibilities, leaders represent all students on committees and bodies within their universities that make decisions. This portrayal, as stated by Olsen (2007) was crucial since it promoted calm and organized learning environment for students. life in academia. According to Olsen, there were more violent student protests in many cases, official routes of consultation and communication were not present. Similarly, Kambuga and Omollo (2017) found that student leaders identified as they play a part in assisting the institutional management in keeping the peace, discipline, and security on campus. Additionally, Kambuga and Omollo think that Student leaders assist management with health and safety planning as part of their duties. educational initiatives. Given this context, one may claim that student leaders' function, or representation, seems to be essential to guarantee a favorable learning environment. as well as the classroom.

According to Benawa (2017), self-efficacy is an important factor in deciding one's success. Self-efficacy is an individual's conviction in their capacity to effectively complete a task or achieve a goal. Individuals with strong self-

efficacy were more inclined to work harder toward their goals. Leadership self-efficacy, grounded in social cognitive theory, was the belief that one has the capabilities and resources to perform a specific task – leadership. This personal belief could change based on different factors of function, such as self-esteem, competency, and environment According to McCormick (2002). It could also be affected by how a person learns behaviors throughout their development, which influences their judgment and decision-making as stated by Bandura (1997).

Research Method:

In this study, researchers used a quantitative method to attain greater knowledge and understanding of the challenges met by student leaders and their effects on their academic performance. It involved the quantification of gathered data and analysis to test a theory. Data were obtained through survey questionnaires and computational tools, and pre-existing statistical data were deployed in the quantitative research design (Babbie, 2007). The researchers used the descriptive correlational method, specifically the descriptive correlational design. The goal of this design was to present a static presentation of situations and build correlations between different variables, as stated by McBurney et al. (2009). The goal was to provide a thorough description of the variables and their relationships without changing them or assuming that one thing caused another. The descriptive correlational design was a non-experimental research method used to describe correlations between variables without changing them. It was especially beneficial when researchers wanted to understand the current connections between 39 variables in their natural setting. This design enabled the study of relationships, patterns, and trends without controlling the variables being studied.

The respondents of the study were the school based organization student leaders in the Education Department. These include Universal Educators (UniEd), Future Educators of Mathematics (FEMATH), Nagkakaisang Mag-aaral sa Filipino (NAMFIL), and Society of Future English Educators (SOFEE). The number of respondents in this study was a total of forty-seven (47) student leaders at Mandaue City College. Purposive sampling was employed in this study since the researchers purposefully chose the respondents. They only included school-based student leaders and excluded the block officers and Educator's Guild, which is the mother organization of the education departments at Mandaue City College. Purposive sampling is a method of non- probability sampling in which sample components are selected as per the researcher's judgment. Researchers frequently feel that by using excellent judgment, they may acquire an accurate sample, saving time and also money.

The researcher utilized a standardized survey questionnaire to gather the necessary data, a well-known and commonly used method in research for quickly collecting and analyzing data from specific populations. The questionnaire was comprised of two (2) parts. The first part contained the profile and general weighted average (GWA) of the respondents. The second part addressed the problems encountered by student leaders, focusing on Time Management, Role Conflict, and Self-efficacy. The researchers employed a 4-point Likert scale based on literature reviews. This scale included 10 indicators to identify time management attitudes from Moneva et al. (2019), 9 items to measure the effect of role conflict from Looti (2023), and 8 items from the Leadership Self-Efficacy Scale from Nguyễn (2016).

Respondents rated their time management based on the frequency of occurrence: Always (4), Often (3), Rarely (2), and Never (1). For role conflict and self-efficacy, respondents rated the level of agreement using the following scale: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The researchers administered the questionnaire using a Google Form to the targeted population within the school. Respondents were given 15 to 20 minutes to complete the questionnaire and were allowed to answer only once to ensure the accuracy and effectiveness of the gathered data.

Findings and Discussion:

This chapter covered the data analysis and interpretation based on the responses of the respondents. The purpose of this chapter was to address the issues determined by the study.

Part 1. Academic Performance of School-based Student Leaders in Mandaue City College.

Table 1. Academic Performance of Student Leaders

Level	Number of Students with the Specified Level
Superior	13 Students

Very Good

34 Students

Legend: Excellent (1.0 and above); Superior (1.1 - 1.5); Very Good(1.6 - 2.0); Good (2.1 - 2.5); Fair (2.6 - 3.0); Failure (3.1 and below)

The table shows that thirty-four (34) student leaders received a very good average grade, and none of them fell below a passing grade. This indicates that the majority of student leaders performed well in their studies. However, it is noteworthy that none achieved an excellent grade, and only thirteen (13) belonged to the superior grade category, emphasizing the high academic standards set. This suggests that there may have been a gap preventing student leaders from reaching the highest level of academic achievement. Understanding their responsibilities, schedules, and roles will make everyone aware of the difficulties these student leaders encounter.

Part 2. Problems Met by Student Leaders and Their Effects to their Academic Performance in terms of Time Management, Role Conflict, and Self-efficacy

Table 2. Time Management

Statement	WM	DE
I do things in order of priority.	3.47	A
I accomplish what needs to be done during the day.	3.51	A
I feel I use my time effectively.	3.23	O
I spend enough time planning.	3.09	O
I am able to meet deadlines without rushing at the last	3.11	O
I spend enough time on academic matters.	3.45	A
I prioritize my list in order of importance, not urgency.	3.19	O
I periodically re-assess my activities in relation to my goals.	3.23	O
My actions are determined primarily by me, not by circumstances or by other people's priorities.	3.49	A
I am satisfied with the way I use my time.	3.40	A

1.00-1.75 = Never; 1.76-2.50 = Rarely; 2.51-3.25 = Often; 3.26-4.0 = Always

Table 2 shows that student leaders from UniEd, NAMFIL, FEMATH, and SOFEE rated statement number 2 the highest, with a weighted mean of 3.51, indicating that student leaders accomplish what needs to be done during the day. Students who are good at managing their time can handle their duties as student leaders and maintain their academic performance by using their time wisely; they can balance their tasks, reduce stress, and optimize productivity. This is supported by Muthoni et al.'s (2019) study, which suggests that the majority of student leaders are capable of adjusting to various situations within the school at the same time facing challenges such as a lack of leadership training and limited resources that will help them to function well in their duties.

In the same table, statement number 4 received the lowest weighted mean, equivalent to 3.09. This suggests that student leaders are facing difficulties in spending time on planning. Student leaders often lack sufficient time for planning due to the additional responsibilities they have in their leadership roles. These responsibilities, such as organizing events and coordinating with team members, require significant time and effort. As a result, they may have less time available for academic tasks, which can negatively impact their academic performance as a student leader. This is supported by the study of Grissom et al. (2015), which indicated that the busy schedule of a student leader, filled with numerous interruptions and problems requiring immediate attention, makes it difficult for them to plan and find time to focus on tasks related to improving their learning.

Table 3. Role Conflict

Statement	WM	DE
I receive conflicting requests from two or more people within the organization.	2.77	A
I do things that are likely to be accepted by one member of organization and not accepted by others.	2.44	D
I am having uncertainties on what is expected from my work.	3.02	A
I am having tasks that have no relation to the job function.	2.61	A
I receive an assignment without the resources or support to complete it.	2.85	A

Sometimes I have to ignore a rule or policy in order to carry out an assignment.	2.68	A	
I work with two or more groups who operate quite differently.		3.12	A
I always feel unable to influence my immediate supervisor's decision and action that affect me.		2.57	A
I always feel that I have to do things on the job that are against my better judgment.	2.61	A	

1.00-1.75 = Strongly Disagree; 1.76-2.50 = Disagree; 2.51-3.25 = Agree; 3.26-4.0 = Strongly Agree

The table shows that the student leaders from four organizations agreed with statement number 7, which says that they work with two or more groups who operate quite differently, with a weighted mean of 3.12. In school, the student leaders were usually called upon and tasked with organizing, designing, and managing events. There were times when events inside the classroom and outside coincided, causing these leaders to have problems with their duties because they were often called to do something else even though they were already engaged in other tasks. This data is supported by the study of Murage et al. (2019), who emphasized that student leaders frequently dealt with the challenge of bringing together academic pursuits with leadership duties, which often led to tensions between these responsibilities.

However, student leaders disagreed with statement number two, indicating that they do things that are likely to be accepted by one member of the organization and not accepted by others. Student leaders disagreed about whether their actions were causing division, but this showed they valued working together and respecting each other. By making sure their decisions included everyone's views, they created a peaceful and productive group. Good communication was key, helping them share ideas, solve conflicts, and build strong relationships. This teamwork not only made their group work better but also showed others the importance of working together and talking openly. This idea is supported by Sholtes (2018), who emphasizes that as a leader and member of an organization, it is important to listen to the voices of each member, as it fosters dedication to the organization.

Table 4. Self-efficacy

Statement	WM	DE
I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself, despite the difficulties that my leadership duties have given me.	3.40	SA
When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them, despite the additional obligations that come with being a student leader.	3.43	SA
In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me while balancing my academic load and leadership duties.	3.36	SA
I believe I can succeed at most in any endeavor to which I set my mind, despite the time limits that come with my student leadership responsibilities.	3.43	SA
I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges, including those that come from the balancing of leadership and academic duties.	3.38	SA
I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks, even while handling the responsibilities of being a student leader.	3.23	A
Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well, despite the challenges that student leaders have while managing their schedules and responsibilities.	3.02	A
Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well academically, despite any distractions or conflicts that may develop as a consequence of my leadership responsibilities.	3.11	A

1.00-1.75 = Strongly Disagree; 1.76-2.50 = Disagree; 2.51-3.25 = Agree; 3.26-4.0 = Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows that student leaders have a sense of self-efficacy, as indicated by their agreement with statements such as when facing difficult tasks, they are certain that they will accomplish them, despite the additional obligations that come with being a student leader and they believe they can succeed at most tasks to which they set their mind. Despite the time limits that come with their student leadership, both got a weighted mean total of 3.43. It was proven that students could perform their duties well when they had trust in themselves and a positive mindset. In leadership

positions, visibility to others was natural. Therefore, having confidence in one's ability when assigned a task is important. This is supported by the study of Benawa (2017), which states that achievements are greatly impacted by self-efficacy and individuals with high self- efficacy tend to exert more effort.

However, student leaders also reported struggling with managing their schedules and responsibilities, as indicated by their disagreement with the statement suggesting they can do most tasks very well. Being a leader took many obligations, not just for oneself, at home, or in the classroom, but also as student leaders. This often resulted in individuals with little time to prepare, resulting in tasks that may not have been done or presented as effectively as they would have wanted. This is supported by the study of Kambuga et al. (2017), which states that student leaders deal with several challenges that might hinder their academic performance, including missed classes, not enough time for individual study, and a lack of effective study habits.

Part 3 Relationship between Problems Met and Academic Performance of Student Leaders

Table 5. Relationship between Problems Met and Academic Performance

Coefficient (r)	N	T Statistics	DF	p-Value	Decision	Interpretation
-0.28	47	-1.98	45	0.026518	Reject	Not Significant

The obtained p-value was below the alpha value, leading the researchers to reject the null hypothesis. This suggested a significant relationship between the problems encountered and the academic performance of student leaders.

Based on the findings, being a student leader had a significant effect on their academic performance, as students encountered difficulties in managing their time. Time management presented a significant problem for student leaders, as they juggled academic pressures, leadership responsibilities, and personal well-being. The combination of these factors often leads to increased stress and busier lifestyles. Student leaders had to find a balance between their academic duties and the demands of their leadership roles within student organizations. Procrastination and poor planning exacerbated this challenge, making it difficult for student leaders to complete assignments and tasks on time. This result was supported by the study of Admin (2023), which indicated that student leaders often faced difficulties in meeting academic deadlines. They also struggled to manage their time efficiently due to problems in areas where they were weakest. This could lead to lower brain function, increased stress and health issues, and decreased effectiveness.

Another issue was role conflict. Based on the gathered data, student leaders had problems with their work because some members of the organization held different perceptions and opinions. Poor communication channels between student leaders and students, as well as between student leaders and school management, could lead to conflicts and a sense of voicelessness among student leaders. Limited resources posed another challenge; student leaders might face obstacles due to resource constraints, hindering their ability to fulfill their roles effectively and leading to conflicts within the organization. Assignments without group support could worsen these issues, as student leaders might find themselves isolated and in conflict when tasked with assignments that lack the necessary group support. This problem was supported by Muthoni (2019), who noted that role conflict became a problem for student leaders because they frequently struggled to balance their academic goals with their leadership responsibilities. This was due to the high expectations and duties associated with leadership roles, which might compete for attention with academic activities. Furthermore, self-efficacy was also a challenge for student leaders. They often experienced difficulties with their self-confidence when they encountered uncertainties due to unclear communication or a lack of understanding about their responsibilities. This lack of clarity undermined their belief in their abilities to effectively carry out their roles. Without clear expectations and guidance, student leaders had difficulty seeing themselves as capable of achieving their goals. Unclear communication from the team, advisers, and school management about their responsibilities worsened this issue, leading student leaders to feel unsure and doubtful about their capabilities. Additionally, insufficient training, resources, and support also diminished their sense of competence, further affecting their self-confidence. This was agreed upon by RJ (2023), who stated that student leaders faced uncertainties about what was expected in their roles due to unclear communication or understanding of their responsibilities reducing their self-efficacy.

In general, based on the findings, Table 3 presented greater numbers and more numerous problems than the other tables. The items in this table often received lower weighted mean ratings, indicating that student leaders experienced significant role conflict, affecting their performance in school and leadership effectiveness. The scores implied more severe challenges in this area than the self-efficacy and time management shown in Tables 4 and 2, respectively. Therefore, based on the statistics presented, role conflict appeared to be the biggest challenge for student leaders to

address. Moreover, time management and self-efficacy problems should also be given attention, as this affects students' academic performance.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study examined the academic performance of student leaders and found that while most received good grades, only a few achieved superior, and none reached the highest academic level which is excellent. This indicates that they encountered problems hindering their academic potential. The three guessed primary issues were proven as challenges for them; these are time management, role conflict, and self-efficacy. Role conflict emerged as the most significant problem, occurring when there was a discrepancy between their perceived responsibilities and the actual demands placed on them. Using Pearson's correlation coefficient, the study demonstrated a significant link between these problems and academic performance, indicating that these issues affected their academic grades. Therefore, the study concluded that there is a significant relationship between the problems met by student leaders and their academic performance.

Limitations and Further Research:

The following are the recommendations made to improve the problems met by student leaders in time management, role conflict, and self-efficacy. Student leaders should prioritize conflict resolution skills and effective communication while also honing time management techniques and seeking support through training programs to enhance their confidence and effectiveness in their roles. Furthermore, teachers can support student leaders by acknowledging their leadership contributions, offering constructive feedback, providing encouragement, organizing development workshops or mentoring programs, and reducing demands on their time and energy. Additionally, parents can collaborate with the school to ensure their child receives the necessary resources and assistance to balance their duties. Moreover, educational institutions should provide resources for time management, flexibility in faculty support, mentorship programs, clear policies, dedicated support services, peer support meetings, and leadership development initiatives tailored to the needs of student leaders. In addition, school administrators should have regular meetings with student leaders and ensure that they are not overloaded with tasks. To fully confirm the findings of this study, future research should employ qualitative research methods to conduct further studies. The school can implement the leadership enhancement program prepared by the researchers.

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